

The Effect of Bilingualism on Social Cognition of Iranian Female Teenagers

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Abstract

The present study investigated the effect of bilingualism on social cognition of Iranian female teenagers. To attain the purpose of the study, 100 Iranian monolingual and bilingual high school female students were selected. They were aged between 14-16 years old. The researcher used social cognition questionnaire to gather the required data. To assess the normality of the obtained data from the questionnaire, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was performed. The researcher used Independent Samples t Tests to find the possible difference between monolinguals' and bilinguals' social cognition. The results revealed that bilingualism had a significant effect on Iranian teenagers' social cognition. In other words, bilingual students showed higher levels of social cognition. The findings have implications for experts in the field of second language learning.

Keywords: Effect of Bilingualism, Social Cognition, Iranian Female Teenagers, language

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a general consensus that individuals are different in their abilities to perform certain tasks. One of these abilities is Social Cognition. Greenwald and Banaji [1] define social cognition, as "the way humans understand and process their interactions with others" (p. 12). This involves perceiving individuals' interaction, making inferences from verbal and nonverbal interaction, and making a perceiving of group dynamics [1].

Individuals use language to share their thoughts and feelings, to make connection with other people, and to understand the world around them [2]. For many individuals, this linguistic context encompasses not only one language but two or more. In fact, most of the world's population is bilingual or multilingual [3].

Lee et al. [4] conducted a study to test the direct, indirect, and complete influence of social cognitive theory on physical activity of high-school students. 341 students participated in this study. The researchers used structural equation modeling to assess the expected correlations among the variables. The results revealed that self-efficacy had the most significant influence on physical tasks. It was also revealed that there was a positive correlation between self-efficacy and physical activity. Self-efficacy also had positive indirect influences on physical activity through perceived advantages and setting goals. The findings of this research showed that the social cognitive theory is an effective model to perceive physical activity among students.

Reyhani , Kamari , Zarei, Nejati [5] investigated the mediating role of emotions in the correlation between social cognition and academic satisfaction. The study was descriptive

and correlational research. The researchers used academic satisfaction questionnaire, achievement emotion questionnaire, and social cognition questionnaire to gather the required data. The findings demonstrated that there is a significant correlation between all variables of this study, which includes academic satisfaction, emotional, and social cognition dimensions. The findings also indicated the significant mediating role of achievement emotion in the relationship between social cognition and academic satisfaction. Based on the obtained results, the researchers concluded that the social cognition and achievement emotion are two of the most important factors for investigating the academic performance and academic satisfaction.

In the simplest definition, bilinguals are people who speak two languages. In the literature, bilingualism has been considered and explained from different views, like linguistic, cognitive and socio-cultural views [3]. Previous studies in bilingualism and cognition considered monolinguals and native speakers as individuals with complete cognitive capacity for learning the native language [6]. Bilinguals were perceived as individuals with only half of the cognitive capacity to learn a L2, as the other half was used with learning the first language [7]. Thus, the main aim of this research is to assess the possible influence of bilingualism on cognitive ability of Iranian teenagers. Among different factors of cognitive ability, the present study aims to explore the effect of bilingualism on social cognition and cognitive flexibility.

2. Method

A total of 100 Iranian high school female students participated in this study. The researcher used the intact classes of students in a high school in Kermanshah. Fifty students were bilinguals who were native speakers of Kurdish and they were able to speak Persian too. The other participants of this study were monolinguals who were only able to speak Persian. The age range of the participants was 14-16. The researcher used available sampling in this study. They were screened according to their self-reporting. That is they were first asked to answer if they use only Persian in their routines or speak in other languages too. To control the influential variable, all the participants were selected from the same school and same major. The overall mean of the students were also considered to make sure that they are homogeneous. So, the students of the one SD below and above the mean in GPA were selected.

2. 1. Instruments

Social Cognition Questionnaire [5] was used to assess participants' level of social cognition. This questionnaire includes 19 items Likert-style with item responses rated from 1 (Never) to 5 (Always). Total scores range from 19 to 95 with higher scores indicating higher level of social cognition. Nejati, Kamari, and Jafari [5] reported the reliability and validity of the questionnaire to be acceptable (Cronbach's $\alpha=0.90$).

2. 2. Data Analysis

To assess the normality of the obtained data from the questionnaires, One-sample Kolmogrov-Smirnow Test was performed. The researcher used descriptive statistics and Independent Samples t Tests to compare the scores of monolingual and bilingual learners. All of the stages of data analysis have been done using SPSS 21.00 software.

3. Results

3. 1. Examining the Normality of Data

Before doing the analysis of data, normality of collected data was measured using One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. This test was performed to find the normality of distribution of data and to make decision about using parametric or nonparametric test to analyze data. In this statistics test, when significance is less than 0.05, the distribution of data is not normal and it is not possible to use parametric tests. When significance is more than 0.05, the distribution of data is normal and it is possible to use parametric tests. The results of this test are reported in Table (1).

Table (1)

One-Sample Kolmogorov- Smirnow Test of Social Cognition of Monolingual and Bilingual Learners

		Social cognition
N		100
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	56.79
	Std. Deviation	25.58
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.118
	Positive	.118
	Negative	-.117
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.175
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.126

a. Test distribution is Normal.

The above table shows the results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test of cognitive flexibility and social cognition. Since, for all of the variables the significance was more than 0.05, the results showed that the data of all of the tests are normal, accordingly, it was possible to use parametric tests to analyze data.

3. 2. Addressing the Research Question

The second research question of the study was: Does bilingualism have a significant effect on social cognition of Iranian teenagers?

To answer the second research question and to investigate the effect of bilingualism on Iranian teenagers' social cognition the researcher used descriptive statistics of the participants' scores of social cognition questionnaire. To find the level of learners' social cognition a set of descriptive statistics was performed. The results of this test are reported in the table (2).

Table (2)

Descriptive Statistics of Social Cognition of Monolingual and Bilingual Learners

	groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Social cognition	monolinguals	50	34.44	11.56	1.63
	bilinguals	50	79.14	13.02	1.84

According to Table 4.4, the mean scores of social cognition of monolingual and bilingual learners are 34.44 and 79.14, respectively. This Table shows that the Std. Deviation of social cognition of monolingual and bilingual learners are 11.56 and 13.02, respectively. As it is clear from this table, the mean score of bilingual learners is higher than the monolingual learners. It shows that bilingual learners enjoy higher level of social cognition than monolingual learners. To find out whether this difference is statistically significant, the researcher used an independent samples t-test. The result of this test is reported in the table (3).

Table (3)

Independent Sample t Test of Social Cognition of Monolingual and Bilingual Learners

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Social cognition	Equal variances assumed	.689	.409	-1.81	98	.000	-4.47	2.46	-4.95	-3.98
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.81	9.6	.000	-4.47	2.46	-4.95	-3.98

According to Table (3), there is a significant statistical difference between the monolingual and bilingual groups in terms of their level of social cognition (Significance is less than 0.05, i.e., 0.00). Accordingly, there was a significant difference between the levels of social cognition of two groups. The following Figure shows the mean scores of social cognition of monolingual and bilingual learners.

Figure (1) Mean scores of social cognition of monolingual and bilingual learners

The above figure shows the mean score of social cognition of monolingual and bilingual learners.

4. Conclusion

The ability to speak two or more languages may bring benefits to individuals since it leads to higher level of cognitive ability. There is a general consensus that bilingual individuals have an advantage in cognitive and mental skill and cognitive flexibility. "The dominant belief at this time is that there is a superiority of divergent thinking abilities among bilinguals" [8].

This study, which intended to examine the effect of second language learning on Iranian teenagers' social cognition, had some findings. The results showed that second language learning has a significant effect on Iranian teenagers' social cognition. This finding implies that bilingual teenagers have a higher level of social cognition than monolinguals. In summary, bilingual students were different from monolingual students in terms of their level of social cognition. Based on the obtained results and in line with previous studied, the researcher concluded that bilingual individuals enjoy higher level of cognitive ability in compare to monolingual individuals and it could be attributed to their ability to speak two languages.

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